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9. Mohammad Refaat Mohammad Abdelaal, Islam Sallam. Green economy themes. Pathway to sustainable urban development. 2019
10. Eu Rural Review. Green economy opportunities for rural Europe. Europe. 2017.
11. Adrian C. Newton and Elena Cantarello. An introduction to the green economy. London, New York. 2014.

Networks.

12. www.greeneconomics.org.uk
13. www.unep.org
14. www.enrd.ec.europa.eu
15. www.oecd.org

THE METHODS FOR MEASURING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP ACTIVITY

NARZULLAEV ELMUROD

Doctoral student of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology
E-mail: narzullaevelmurod@gmail.com, phone.: (+99891) 363-61-61

Abstract:

Objectives: The main objective of this study is measuring capability of a wide range of social enterprises. The theoretical basis of the scale is supported by empirical research in the social sector. The scale provides a valid, reliable tool for measuring a wide range of SE in firms which meets different types of properties that required for measuring scales in the validity, social sciences or reliability.

Methods. Within the framework of the problem of measuring efficiency social entrepreneurship describes the most common and popular approaches and measurement methods forms and content achieved by social entrepreneurs the results of their activities. The most common problems of measuring and evaluating social outcomes and social effects faced by social entrepreneurs who firmly believe that indicators of accuracy and interpretation of results allow them to deepen your knowledge and understanding of the true situation organization and their real status in the community of social entrepreneurs.

Results. The results of this study analyses that the measuring the activity of social entrepreneurship is integral part of developing and managing SE in every single society. It was evident that social entrepreneurship has remarkable contribution in triple-bottom-line components of community development. In order to measure the activity variety of methods are analyzed alongside and in order to calculate the efficiency of SE new formula is offered.

Conclusion. The development of social entrepreneurship has become widespread throughout the world, including in Uzbekistan. In view of the rapid spread of this new direction of entrepreneurial activity, it became necessary to develop an appropriate methodology for a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of social enterprises. This article will be of interest to undergraduates, graduate students, entrepreneurs and researchers in the field of social entrepreneurship.

Keywords: social entrepreneurship; social and financial value; social and economic efficiency, social project, social benefit, measuring social effect;

Introduction. The social sphere is a complex of both public and private institutions whose activities are aimed at sustainable socio-economic development of the regions, maintaining and improving the quality of life of the population. Branches of the social sphere are called upon to meet

the material, spiritual, educational, medical, cultural and social needs of the population. The most important social category that characterizes the general level of well-being, as well as the degree of satisfaction of human needs, is the quality of life.

Managing the quality of life of the population is a process that "is an integral part of a complex and multifactorial system, which includes many indicators and indicators to measure its level"⁷. The presence of a developed social infrastructure is designed to ensure a high standard of living in the country.

Methods. Today in the community of social entrepreneurs a significant number of those who are not sufficiently aware of existing approaches and methods for assessing social the impact of their activities. Foreign experience shows that the need to measure social outcomes and social effects is constantly increasing, since social organizations must constantly prove their social significance.

When we are talking about methods of describing the social effect. Descriptive techniques ("stories and cases") aim to receiving feedback from stakeholders on the achieved social results and social impact, but their measurement is not held. Descriptive techniques, therefore, reveal results and best practices, factoring out efficiency¹⁰.

However, due to the lack of a standard system and convenient tools for measuring social outcomes left to discretion of management and stakeholders on voluntary beginnings - based on faith, intuition and case analysis. Many social entrepreneurs do not measure social results, and few measure, but not systematically⁸. Consider the current practice of assessing social effects, socially significant results obtained in the field of social entrepreneurship. Most social entrepreneurs use common form of measurement, which is passing on stories representing examples of success to their sponsors and other interested parties. Most case histories are critical to uncovering qualitative information⁹.

⁷ Ageenko A.V. The problem of assessing the satisfaction of the population with the quality of social services for the purpose of managing the quality of life in municipalities

⁸ Рождественская Н.В., Богуславская С.Б., Боброва О.С. Оценка эффективности проектов некоммерческих

организаций, социального предпринимательства 2016.-168 с.

⁹ Тимохович А.Н., Никурадзе О.И. Измерение эффективности предпринимательства / 2020. №7.

С.193-198.

¹⁰ Ageenko A.V. The problem of assessing the satisfaction of the population with the quality of social services for the purpose of managing the quality of life in municipalities // Economics, management, finance: Collection of conference materials. – Perm: Mercury, 2011. – 123 p. – P. 5-8.

Figure 1. The advantages of Descriptive techniques method¹¹

Another method do measure SE is the logic of a socially oriented program which describes the connection specific actions taken and the implementation of the mission program through the achievement of the objectives of the program and the decision tasks. This logic has a hierarchical structure: upon successful performing actions, the tasks of the program are solved, while solving tasks, the goal of the program is achieved, and the achievement of the goal of the program contributes to solving a larger problem (implementation of the mission of the program)¹¹.

The logical model of a program is a structured visual understanding of the

relationship of resources invested in the program, applied actions and strategies, and those social changes that which need to be achieved. The logical model is a tool with which you can plan a project, analyze current activities, as well as present project stakeholders information in a lapidary and accessible form.

The logical model (theory of change) is a tool control used to improve the structure of the program not only at the design level, but also at the implementation level project. It includes such strategic components project, as inputs, results, end products, impact.

¹¹ Фейербах Л. Сущность христианства // Избранные философские произведения. Т.2-. М.:1955.-420 с

The chain of results to measure social effect

Figure 2. The chain of result to measure social effect

Discussion. In the last decade, the idea of social enterprise has been gaining popularity, which set their task not only to achieve profit, but also to solve other problems. If a few years ago, the social entrepreneur was soon an exceptional figure, then now the phenomenon of social entrepreneurship is becoming mass. Don't start the chain Our reaction, which in the early 70s of the last century made a popular effect: appearance of the first investors increased the interest in the industry and, accordingly, the number of entrepreneurs. Spiral of the beginning unrolling¹². The number of entrepreneurs and investors increased. The same thing happens and now, in the sphere of social entrepreneurship, the number of enterprises and the number of projects.

Evaluation of the effectiveness of promising social projects, as well as the socio-economic activities of social enterprises in general, can be carried out at different levels of the country's economy. However, it should be noted that the existing methodological approaches to assessing the performance of social enterprises, the set of indicators included in the calculation of efficiency, as well as their priority for each level may differ¹³. In addition, a set of measures that is effective at one level may be associated with some costs that will reduce the effectiveness of

activities at another level. Still, it can also be the other way around. Thus, when evaluating efficiency at the enterprise level, first of all, emphasis is placed on the economic results of the implementation of current and prospective projects and their impact on the performance of a social enterprise. Naturally, given the social orientation of the enterprise, the social consequences of the activities carried out by it within the framework of the goals of the project should be taken into account¹⁴.

The success of many social enterprises or a social designs carried out by own formulated programm in terms of achieving the final result. For its evaluation, such concepts as effectiveness, efficiency, quality assessment are most often used, which are formed on the basis of the tasks and goals of both the social enterprise itself and the implementation of the social policy of the society, which provides social services and the provision of social services to the population within a certain region or the whole country.

As part of the implementation of any social project, the goals of the enterprise can be both universal and specific, due to a certain type of social enterprise and oriented in accordance with the characteristics of the region in which the project is being implemented.

¹² A.A. Plyukhina, "Improvement of the method for assessment of social enterprises' activity", - 2016 Moscow

¹³ Минаев А.В. Критерии и методы оценки проектов социального предпринимательства // Труды

Московского физико-технического института. – 2011.

¹⁴ Минаев А.В. Критерии и методы оценки проектов социального предпринимательства // . – 2011

Results. The analysis of the performance of a social enterprise can be described by the following algorithm, which includes¹⁵:

1. Research and preliminary strategic marketing planning. At this stage, the general socio-economic situation of the region is studied, a number of problems of its development are identified, as well as the perception by certain groups of the population of the nature of social projects, their main goals and results, changes and impacts arising in the course of practical activity

2. The next stage is the definition of the target audience for which the social project is aimed, the identification of direct or indirect consumers of public goods and their expected end result from the implementation of the project.

3. Establishing the boundaries of the analysis. Within the framework of this step, specific goals and directions of the impact of the social project are determined, as well as the period and parameters of functioning.

4. Development of a scorecard and development of indicators. At this stage, the nature of social benefits, the nature of the impact and changes that occur during the social project are substantiated. Social benefits are formed, and the social value created in the process of project implementation is determined.

5. Definition of forecasts. As part of this step, funding sources are identified, financial performance and reporting are examined, and the impact of various performance indicators on social, economic, and environmental outcomes being created is assessed.

6. Calculation of the social efficiency of the project. The stage provides for the

calculation of the reduced cash flows for the project based on the collected data, the developed implementation model and forecast data. The calculation of such indicators as the payback period, profitability of invested capital, and the amount of actual expenses are taken into account. It is important to analyze the risk factors at the project implementation stage.

7. Formation of reporting and development of measures to improve the activities of the social enterprise.

Evaluation of the performance of social enterprises is based on performance indicators and criteria. Efficiency and quality assessment is an integral part of the overall quality assurance system, within which each social enterprise seeks to understand the process and result of its work¹⁶.

Social performance indicators are determined on the basis of economic and statistical reporting data, based on the results of a survey, using the method of expert assessments, and others. At the same time, some of the indicators have a very conditional value, while others cannot be expressed quantitatively.

Based on the existing traditional assessment methods, we propose to introduce and use an integral coefficient (KEF) to assess the effectiveness of a social enterprise, which includes a set of criteria (K_{1-n}), that is an indicator of the social effectiveness of the social project, the efficiency of a social enterprise; the Weisbrod social index, which reflects "the relationship between the types of financial receipts of an enterprise and the nature of the services it provides or the products it produces"; coefficient of social profitability; payback period of a social project, etc.¹⁷:

$$Kef = K1*i1 + K2*i2 + K3*i3 + K4*i4 + Kn*in, (1)$$

¹⁵ Ageenko A.V. The problem of assessing the satisfaction of the population with the quality of social services for the purpose of managing the quality of life in municipalities // Economics, management, finance:– 2011

¹⁶ Martin, R. L., & Osberg, S. Social entrepreneurship The case for definition. Stanford social innovation – 2007.

¹⁷ Catherine L.H. Canadian Social Enterprises: Who Gets the Non-Earned Income?–2016

there $i_{1-4, n}$ – coefficient significance.

As one of the most important criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of a social project, we take the indicator of the social effect from the implementation of a social project (K_{SP}), which, based on the methodology for evaluating the effectiveness of an investment project with a social focus, can be calculated using the formula:

$$K_{SP} = K_{RE} * K_{SE}, (2)$$

there K_{RE} – coefficient of regional usefulness

K_{SE} – coefficient of social efficiency

Social efficiency implies a positive impact from the implementation of a social project for the population, which can be expressed in improving the quality of life or increasing the supply of new social services, in the regularity, timeliness, and also in increasing the availability of their provision.

Conclusion. In the modern civilized world, the assessment of social results and effects obtained in the process of implementation social projects in social organizations, becomes essential elements of their relationship with employees and volunteers, donors, beneficiaries and the state. That's why the community of social entrepreneurs interested in eliminating the main problems along the way development of a unified system for assessing social results and effects. Here is a list of them:

➤ lack of simple and practical tools that causes irregular assessment of social results and effects by social entrepreneurs;

➤ underestimation of the quality of life changes beneficiaries or society;

➤ false goals and indicators: the choice of more "light" beneficiaries to provide services for the purpose demonstrating great success in achieving social results;

➤ proportionality and balance: efforts, invested in the social performance measurement system and the level exactly must be proportionate;

➤ excessive bureaucracy: a system for measuring social results should help, not take away from the social entrepreneur already scarce resources;

To conclude it is necessary to change the attitude towards the evaluation of all internal and external stakeholders interacting with social projects. Social impact assessment is extremely important aspect of the development of social entrepreneurship, which means a way of solving or mitigating the problems that exist in society.

References

1. Ageenko A.V. The problem of assessing the satisfaction of the population with the quality of social services for the purpose of managing the quality of life in municipalities // Economics, management, finance: Collection of conference materials. – Perm: Mercury, 2011. – 123 p. – P. 5-8.
2. Минаев А.В. Критерии и методы оценки проектов социального предпринимательства //– 2011. – Т. 3. – № 3. – С. 153-158.
3. Синдяшкина Е.Н. Вопросы оценки видов социального эффекта при реализации инвестиционных проектов // Проблемы прогнозирования. – 2010. – № 1. – С. 140-147.
4. Catherine L.H. Canadian Social Enterprises: Who Gets the Non-Earned Income?-2016
5. Рождественская Н.В., Богуславская С.Б., Боброва О.С. Оценка эффективности проектов некоммерческих организаций, социального предпринимательства 2016.-168 с.
6. Васильева М. Сеть пансионатов для пожилых «Опека» собирается продавать франшизу в регионах *Электронный ресурс+ // Портал «Новый бизнес:

социальное предпринимательство». – 2015. – 12 ноября. – Режим доступа: <http://www.nb-forum.ru/interesting/stories/opeka-idet-vo-franshiz.html>

7. Marta Peris-Ortiz, Carlos Rueda-Armengot "Is it possible to measure social entrepreneurship in firms?" – 2015 Spain

8. Петрова В. Фитнес городских улиц // Портал «Новый бизнес: социальное предпринимательство». – 2014. – 4 августа.

9. Кузнецова Е.С., Богданова А.С. Оценка эффективности проектов в сфере государственного и муниципального управления – 2012. – Т. 15. – № 1. – С. 195-198.

10. Anastasia A. Plyukhina, "Improvement of the method for assessment of social enterprises' activity", - 2016 Moscow

11. Wee-Liang, J.Williams, Teck-Meng. "Defining the 'Social' in 'Social Entrepreneurship': Altruism and Entrepreneurship." The International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal. P. 353-365 – 2005.

12. Enterprising Ideas. What is a Social Entrepreneur? PBS Foundation – 2018. Enterprising Ideas. What is a Social Entrepreneur? PBS Foundation. –2018.

13. Martin, R. L., & Osberg, S. Social entrepreneurship: The case for definition. Stanford social innovation Review. – 2007.

14. Фейербах Л. Сущность христианства // Избранные философские произведения. Т.2-. М.:1955- 420 с

15. Vilensky P.L., Livshits V.N., Smolyak S.A. Evaluation of the efficiency of investment projects theory and practice. Moscow: - 2002. 888 p.

16. Viscisi, W. Kip, Aldy Joseph E. The Value of a Statistical Life: A Critical Review of Market Estimates Throughout The World // Journal of Risk and Insurance - 2003. V. 27, N. 1, P. 5--76.

ANALYSIS OF THE MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN

NARZULLAEV ELMUROD

Doctoral student of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology
E-mail: narzullaevmurod@gmail.com, phone.: (+99891) 363-61-61

Abstract:

Objectives: The main objective of this study is analyzing and measuring the capability of improving and developing social enterprises in Uzbekistan. The theoretical basis of the scale is supported by empirical research in the social sector. On other hand, finding out both strengths and weaknesses on managing and developing environmental social entrepreneurship in our country also was our main aim in this article.

Methods. In this article we used SWOT analysis in order to identify the current condition of environmental social entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan. Besides that, variety kinds of tables and diagrams also created by author based on the information given by statistic committee.

Results. The results of this study analyses that social enterprises are required to report on the social and/or environmental benefits they bring to society, but in most countries, a uniform reporting form and criteria have not yet been developed in the area of control. In foreign practice, there are different definitions of social entrepreneurship, which sometimes contradict each other. According to experts, the complexity of developing a single legal approach to defining the term social entrepreneurship is explained by the following circumstances.

Conclusion. To conclude, environmental social entrepreneurship can be seen as an integral part of every single society and government future plans because of it vitalness and importance in today's world. Because, tons of environmental and social problems are improving day by day instead of reducing. In order to solve aforementioned problems, social entrepreneurship is a most accurate choice in developing countries like Uzbekistan.

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